

The Childhood of Empire and the Politics of Representation: A Study of Ex-Child, Rudyard Kipling's *The Jungle Books*

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Abstract: *Mowgli, the child protagonist of The Jungle Book, belongs to the created space of the childhood dream of the Sahib Kipling. In the book, the ideal space for the child and that of the British Empire are in a state of equilibrium. India is a romantic playground of the ex-child Kipling and the playground of imperialism for the Sahib Kipling. Therefore, the constancy of his childhood dream is always dependent on his illusion of the constancy of the Empire as a positive source of power. So, Mowgli is an outsider very easily accepted as superior and given attributes of racial superiority. Therefore, The Jungle Books, beneath its allegorical framework, brings together the politics of representations associated with children's literature and the literature of the Empire.*

Keywords: Colonialism, Kipling, *The Jungle Book*, British Raj, Children's literature.

Joseph Rudyard Kipling, or the Sahib Kipling, the unofficial laureate of the British Empire, as the critics of the post-colonial era have called him, is also a master storyteller for children. But sadly, and unfortunately, Kipling, the great weaver of children's fiction, is often overlooked for his imperialistic stand. Therefore, literary critics often find it hard to place him among the literary canons of his time or any time, especially in the aftermath of colonial history. Most literary critics choose to avoid him or give him a passing mention unless their focus is on the issues of empire, as in Joseph Bristow's *Empire Boys* (1991) or Daphne Kutzer's *Empire's Children* (2002). Recent important studies on children's literature, such as Perry Nodelman's *The Hidden Adult* (2008), brush him off with the courtesy of mentioning. What went against him is that he took a very clear political stand for the empire, even at the expense of its evil effects, which he did not see or did not want to see. This is perhaps a simplified version of the view, but since it is a very sensitive issue, very few have tried to get involved in it, probably for fear of inviting unwanted questions and criticism.

However, Kipling's political setback and negative literary reviews do not affect the readership of Kipling's children's classics, such as *The Jungle Book* (1893), *The Second Jungle Book* (1894), *Kim* (1901), *Just So Stories* (1902), and *Puck of Pook's Hill* (1906) over time. These books have never been out of print since their first publication and have been avidly read by adults and children for generations in the British Isles and the previous colonies for over a hundred years. In Nineteen Forty-Five, when Kipling's reputation had much declined, Hilton Brown wrote: "...far too much has been made of his 'Imperialism' by those with good political reasons for purveying a distorted version. There is much to be said for the view of the New York columnist twenty years later who wrote, at a time [in the 1920s] when his countrymen were smarting under Kipling's criticism of their part in the last war: 'What difference does it make if he is an insufferable Tory? He wrote *The Jungle Book*. Has everybody forgotten that?'" (*The Jungle Book* no page). The same notion is held by the beloved children's fiction writer of India, Ruskin Bond; in the 'Introduction' to *The Adventure of Mowgli*, he writes: "In England, public opinion went against Kipling during his lifetime, and he was ridiculed as a racist and champion of empire at a time when empires were going out of fashion. 'Why, then, are you still reading Kipling in India?' asked a puzzled visitor

recently. The answer he received was simple: ‘Forget the politics. He wrote *The Jungle Books*, didn’t he?’” (Kipling, Intro)

However, as the children-readers of Kipling’s stories, we may be happy to skip the notorious task of criticism and focus on reading only, but as an adult burdened with the whole discourse of Rudyard Kipling’s reception in the literary circle, it leaves us with no choice but to tread on the unwanted waters. It might be true to say that Kipling’s stories are keenly appreciated by those who read them first in childhood, and the experience of the reading comes back to them in their later lives. The experience associated with the reading of eight Mowgli stories of *The Jungle Books* and their magical impression on a child reader’s mind is certainly something that one wants to live with forever. Kingsley Amis writes: “*The Jungle Book* and *The Second Jungle Book* were once enormously popular with children, and even today not many people need to be told who Mowgli and Shere Khan are, though this knowledge must sometimes come only from having seen the Disney film. The judgment of an adult in such cases is not worth much” (Underwood, no page). Still, Kipling cannot escape the imperialistic decoding of his texts, as Jan Montefiore asserts: “Imperialism is an important focus for critics of children’s literature, and Kipling was unquestionably an imperialist whose views not only coloured but, in some respects, inspired his writings for children” (Booth 96).

The Jungle Books were written in Vermont, USA, and the stories initiated a phase in Kipling’s literary career when he seriously thought of becoming a children’s writer. It was a time when his wife Carrie Balestier was pregnant with his child, and this had set him thinking about children and childhood, reawakening his own inner child, long dormant’ (Allen 322). He wrote “The Potter Princess” for *St. Nicholas Magazine* at that time. The story focuses on him and his little sister Trix’s Bombay childhood. This is the time he also proposed the plot of *Kim*, a story about ‘a small boy who got a blessing and a ghost-dagger from a Thibetan Lama who came down from Thibet in search of a miraculous river that washed away all sin (the river that gushed out when the Bodhisat’s arrow struck in the ground) and how these two went hunting for it together—the old priest with his priestly Tam O’shanater hat and the young English child’ (quoted in Allen, 324). But he had to put aside that project for something that occupied him for some time, i.e., ‘the Indian jungle and its denizens, human and wild’ (Allen 324). Ruskin Bond describes the stories of *The Jungle Book* as “tales that are full of nostalgia and longing for the land he had left behind” (Kipling, Intro).

Rudyard Kipling later looked back on his childhood in India as ‘a time untrammelled happiness’. He felt a natural closeness to the land and people, and the feeling was to stay with him for the rest of his life. The happiness that the child Ruddy (which became his nickname) attained for the first years of his life owed far more to the companionship of the household servants than to his parents, who probably had little time to spare. Ruddy and Trix, his little sister, in the company of the household servants, mingled with a different India from that of their parents. They could speak the lingua franca, Urdu. In British India, it was a fact in the Anglo-Indian circle that first the European child must be spoiled by the servants and then sent Home to England to repair the damage caused by the amalgamation of native socio-linguistic culture. So Ruddy and his baby sister, along with their parents, moved to England on 15 April 1871, and this marked the ending of their innocence and the beginning of their hardship in exile. As for the custom, the Anglo-

Indians chose to keep their children in the custody of their relatives before docking in India. But it was not the case with Ruddy and his sister Trix; the custody was entrusted to a married couple who advertised for custody of a foster child whose parents were stationed in India. The aforesaid paid foster parents, Mrs. Sarah Holloway and her husband, lived in Lorne Lodge, at 4 Campbell Road, Havelock Park, Southsea, which in Ruddy's and Trix's semi-fiction would become the 'House of Desolation'. In *Something of Myself*, Kipling writes: Lorne Lodge was "an establishment run with full vigour of the Evangelical as revealed to the Woman. I had never heard of Hell, so I was introduced to it in all its terror." Ruddy's confidence was totally shattered. Mrs. Holloway, to break the will of the boy, subjected him to beating, solitary confinement, and other means of torture, which were to continue for the next six and a half years he spent under her custody. His autobiographical short story 'Baa, Baa, Black Sheep' narrated this in the fictional self of Punch and his little sister Judy, who were abandoned by their parents to the ministrations of Aunty Rosa. From there, Ruddy went on to receive an education in United Services College at Westward Ho! under the kind guardianship of Cornell Price, and read the current literature from Browning to Swinburne, and gradually, forgetting his mid-childhood debacle, inclined to become a thoroughbred English Sahib.

However, the childhood or adolescence represented in children's literature is associated with fun, adventure, imagination, friendship, companionship, and obviously, safety attained at last is, in fact, not always there in reality. Judy Blume wrote, "Childhood can be a terrible time of life. No kid wants to stay a kid. It is only adults who have forgotten who say, 'If only I could be a kid again.' The fantasy of childhood is to be an adult." (qtd in Maybin 13-14). Rabindranath Tagore, in his collection of poems in the anthology, *Shishu Bholanath* (Child Shiva), talks of this as the imaginative space of a child to counter the monopoly of the adult world; it helps them to escape into a fantasy world of play when reality becomes too rough. Likewise, children's literature is rather an adult writer's projection of his ideal vision of childhood, as Freud, in his brilliant essay "Creative Writers and Daydreaming," informs us that the creative writer finds the real world extremely painful, and he escapes into a world of fantasy of which he is the sole master. This world is a kind of child's play. Just as a child derives great pleasure from playing the games of adults, the creative writers recall the plays or games of their childhood to gain pleasure. In Kipling, this is not an exception; he wanted to forget his own childhood, and being an ex-child, wanted to create an alternative childhood that would remain forever.

Now, when he is recreating his childhood as an ex-child and as a Sahib, India becomes a problematic space. India is a romantic playground of this ex-child Kipling and the playground of imperialism for the Sahib Kipling. Therefore, the constancy of his childhood dream is always dependent on his illusion of the constancy of the Empire as a positive source of power. What Kipling could not see is that this is not the case from the indigenous point of view. In this context, we may quote Peter Hunt who writes: "...texts for children do not portray childhood as it was or is, but portray childhood as the writers wished it to be seen for political, sociological or dramatic reasons." (Maybin 14). So, Mowgli of *The Jungle Books* is an outsider very easily accepted as superior, and given attributes of racial superiority. With especial reference to Mowgli stories John McClure argues that these stories amount to "a fable of imperial education and rule, with Mowgli behaving towards

the beasts as the British do to the Indians...to be above yet to belong, to be obeyed as a God and loved as a brother, this is Kipling's dream for the imperial ruler, a dream that Mowgli achieves" (McClure 60).

Therefore, the rhetoric of the *Jungle Book* and Mowgli's supreme position among the animal kind in the jungle can be seen as a metaphor for the European imperialist's daydream of mastery among the natives. On the other hand, the book is a story of a child's heroic adventure and triumph in the true sense of the British imperialistic codes: in "Kaa's Hunting," as child Mowgli's intelligence saves him from the lawless *Bandar-Log* or the monkey pack; in 'Tiger! Tiger!', he was found to be much more physically and mentally formidable, and he plots the death of Shere Khan under the hooves of cattle driven by his wolf-brothers, used by him as sheepdogs. He also punished the villagers for their wickedness by 'Letting in the Jungle'; and in 'Red Dog' he saves the 'free people' of the jungle from the savage raid of the red dogs by setting trap at the bees lairs by the river edge with his resourcefulness and by the wisdom of Kaa for the invaders which give them a better hand in the battle which they eventually win. By the end of the book in 'The Spring Running', he achieved a supreme mastery over the jungle people, in other words, tames and adopts the wildness within him.

Therefore, the trope of the jungle is used in a very idealistic sense of the children's world; it is a wonderful place of children's dreams—wild and secure, which also makes them learn the adult laws on their way to adulthood. Mowgli, the '[w]olf boy, child of the jungle...stands for innocence, nobility, purity of heart and mind. His friends and companions in the wild—Baloo the bear, Bagheera the black panther, Kaa the great snake—represent all that is good and generous, while his enemy, Shere Khan the tiger, represents fear and hatred" (Kipling, intro, no page). However, under all these metaphoric connotations, the story also reaffirms the strange wilderness of the British colonial territories in the eyes of the West. Mowgli is both a "Worsworthian child of nature" and "a boy scout" in the wild jungle of the Far East (Stewart 116). The India that Kipling left as a boy is certainly a place of romance for him, and the stories in the *Jungle Books* are filled with this romance; Rosemary Sutcliff calls the book "the small unlined pocket of childhood in [him]self" (Booth 75). In this context, Ruskin Bond's introductory remark on the book is significant; he states, "Kipling's fascination with India was a boy's interest. He was enraptured by the bright living panorama, all the colours in that wonderful box of paints that make up India. He was caught up by the soldiers and the animals, the jungle and the frontier, the supernatural, lonely men in far-flung outposts, blood and thunder, and the everlasting hills. It was all romance to him. He did not see—because he did not want to see—the political ferment, the struggling idea of nationhood, the religious thought, the wisdom of India" (Kipling, Intro. no page).

Therefore, Kipling saw India through the colourful glass of an outsider; and this image he merged with the imperialistic ideology of the Western institutions making; the code of this ideologies is variedly displayed throughout the stories: the jungle is place which supports free adventure a child dream of but the place does not lack discipline; the versified 'Law of the Jungle' taught to the Wolf-Pack sets a distinctly public school value on cleanliness and self-control: "...wash daily from nose-tip to tail-tip; drink deeply but not too deep" (*The Second Jungle Book* 29). The 'Jungle Law' is not neo-Darwinian law of the survival of the fittest; it is an elaborate civil and criminal code which is set for a reason and is "as perfect as

time and custom can make it” (3). Apart from unruly monkeys or *Bandar-log*, the animal lives in a society govern law under Hati, ‘the master of the jungle’, (16) who trumpets the ‘Water Truce’ in “How Fear Come”. The animals also understand the deal of exchange as when Mowgli’s acceptance in the Wolf-Pack is bought by Bagheera’s gift of a bull: “The cub can be bought for a price. It is the law” (21). Therefore, Mowgli’s fostering as a man cub happens away from the ‘Man-Pack’ (the human villagers) within the boundaries securely drawn by the ‘Jungle-Law’ which is ultimately ratified by the distantly powerful justice of ‘the English at Khanhiwara’ where Messua, the foster mother of Mowgli, and her husband are sent for protection from the lawless villagers. The idea that people need law to be free, and it is metaphorically expressed in the expression ‘Free People’ what the Wolf-Pack, which follows the law, is called. The wolves themselves discover after a period of lawlessness how much they need the law; at the end of “Tiger! Tiger!” the leaderless members of the former ‘Free People’ cry, “lead us again, O Akela.... for we be sick of this lawlessness, and we would be the Free People once more.” There is always a price to be paid for being free; therefore, Bagheera altogether denies them the opportunity: “Yet fought you for freedom, and it is yours. Eat it, O wolves” (Kipling 81-82). Therefore, all these preachings are not without their due share of imperialistic ideology. Mowgli, who has to leave the jungle of childhood to return to the Man-Pack — to embrace the adult world, learns all the behavioural codes and discipline of imperialist ideology through which he gains mastery over the animal world and may eventually end up applying in his dealings with the adult world. Mowgli is different from the outset; he learns all the talk of the animals from Baloo, which helps him to dominate over all the animal species in the jungle. He is, all in all, a hybrid figure, which is reaffirmed by the Mother Wolf’s naming him after a frog, an amphibious creature who learns the code of the “Law of the Jungle” and is now free to translate it in his world. Therefore, Mowgli’s fostering in the jungle is “undoubtedly fired by the pities of empire and by the imperialist fantasy of mastering otherness” (Booth 108).

However, neither the jungle, which is a metaphor for the imaginative space of a child, nor the empire, which is a representative of an alien race, remains forever. Mowgli, who becomes the benevolent benefactor of jungle people, always remains rather distinct from them and always a threat to them, which is evident when Bagheera tells Mowgli: “The others they hate thee because their eyes cannot meet thine; because thou art wise; because thou hast pulled out thorns from their feet—because thou art a man.” (Kipling 16). John McClure finds no difference between Mowgli’s cold gaze and the “conventional ‘White Man’ mastering hapless natives” (Booth 107). Though he is given the status of the ‘master of the jungle,’ he does not behave like an imperial ruler. His mastery over the beasts is totally dependent on the consent of the beasts that love him and fear him for his great qualities. Nonetheless, Mowgli’s humanity makes him apart from the animals; his possession of fire affirms his high position and divides him and the beasts who fear ‘the red flower’ (fire). By the end of the last Mowgli story, viz., ‘The Spring Running’, we see that “The Jungle People who used to fear him for his wits feared him now for his strength, and when he moved quietly on his own affairs the mere whisper of his coming cleared the wood path.” (Kipling 200). Even the fierce Bagheera is cowed down before Mowgli: “Mowgli looked at him lazily from under his long eyelashes, and as usual, the panther’s head dropped. Bagheera knew his master” (201). Still, Mowgli remains alienated in the ‘Time of New Talk’; the jungle

people cannot follow him then. It is the time when “he sulks like a spoilt child...because he is ignored by his animal friends in their spring fever, which he cannot simply share with them because beautiful as the Jungle is, it holds no mate for him” (Booth 107). It is here that Mowgli realises his difference from the jungle people. Mowgli is 17 then—the phase of adolescence which marks the beginning of adulthood. Therefore, it is only right that he must go back to the ‘man pack’, leaving his childhood abode of thrill and adventure after mastering the codes of the adult world. This departure of Mowgli from the jungle of his childhood serves a twofold purpose; he not only leaves the jungle as a grown-up but also the ‘master of the jungle’. So, the jungle is both an ideal space of joy, happiness, adventure, and fun for a child, and the symbolic locale of imperial rule; and Kipling perhaps knew both would end sometime.

Nonetheless, Mowgli is the wistful child of Kipling’s India, ‘the paradise garden of his childhood, his land of lost delight’ (Allen 363). The Sahib Kipling could have retained this paradise only through the mastery of others by benevolent imperial rule, which Mowgli did, but it proves impossible. Though Mowgli achieves a perfect equilibrium between the world of the master and that of the other, this is not without the foretelling: “Thou art of the jungle and not of the jungle” (Kipling 126) and “thou must go back to men at last” (17). Therefore, the Mowgli tales in *The Jungle Books* beneath its allegorical framework brings together the politics of representations associated with children’s literature and the literature of the Empire which perhaps becomes much more vocal because it is written by a man who received negative criticism for his oversimplified political view of British imperialism, but as Nirad C. Chaudhuri asserts “Kipling the writer always able to rise above Kipling the political man...” (qtd in Baise 106). Children-readers across generations fall in love with Mowgli; whether he is a symbolic representative of the empire or not matters little to them. Perhaps we remember Kipling for this representation of a happy, adventurous childhood in the Mowgli Stories, which can mesmerise a child and his imaginative and intuitive world. Still, the imperial clichés remain a part of the fictional childhood represented by the Forster ex-child of colonial India, which, to a judicious adult reader, becomes a problematic area to be overlooked.

Works Cited

- Booth, Howard J., editor. *The Cambridge Companion to Rudyard Kipling*. UK, Cambridge UP, 2011.
- Charles, Allen. *Kipling Sahib: India and the Making of Rudyard Kipling*. Great Britain, Abascus, 2013.
- Jennifer, Baise, editor. *Children’s Literature Review*. Detroit, Gale Group, 2001.
- Kipling, Rudyard. *The Adventure of Mowgli*. Gurgaon, Puffin Books, 2009.
- ---. *The Second Jungle Book*. London, Macmillan, 1957.
- MacClure, John. *Kipling and Conrad: The Colonial Fiction*. Cambridge, MA, Harvard UP, 1981.
- Maybin, Janet, and Nicola J. Watson, editors. *Children’s Literature: Approaches and Territories*. Great Britain, Palgrave Macmillan, 2009.
- Stewart, J. I. M. *Rudyard Kipling*. London, Gollancz, 1966.
- “The Jungle Book: The Critics.” *Reader’s Guide*, 10 Sept. 2008, www.kiplingsociety.co.uk/rg_jungle_criticism.htm.